

The Effect of Manganese and Bismuth on the Properties and Behavior of Calcium Phosphate

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Abstract:

The human bone contains 70% of calcium phosphate. Calcium phosphates were soared in biomedical research and were approached for a broad range of orthopedic and dental applications. The bioceramic material used in many biomedical applications such as dental and orthopedic application which is the total knee replacement. The main purpose of this work is to study the effect of calcium phosphate when doped with manganese and bismuth. Calcium phosphate ranging from 100 Wt%, 99.65 Wt%, 99.45Wt%, 99.25 Wt%, and 99.05Wt%, manganese constant weight percentage 0.25 Wt%, and bismuth ranging from 0 Wt%, 0.1 Wt%, 0.3 Wt%, 0.5 Wt, and 0.7 Wt%. The green samples were sintered at constant sintered temperature 1300°C. The highest value of density of 4.52 g/cm³ was obtained for CaP 99.25 Wt% doped 0.25 Wt% Mn and Bi 0.5 Wt%. For the shrinkage rate when CaP 99.25 Wt% doped 0.25 Wt% Mn and Bi 0.5 Wt% shrinks 18.20% this was beneficial to know the stronger and higher quality for the material. CaP 99.25 Wt% doped 0.25 Wt% Mn and Bi 0.5 Wt% was able to achieve the highest hardness of 378.3 HV. Maximum young's modulus of 5.74 GPa was observed for CaP 99.45 Wt% doped 0.25 Wt% Mn and Bi 0.3 Wt% and ultimate compressive strength of 15093.2 N was observed for CaP 99.45 Wt% doped 0.25 Wt% Mn and Bi 0.3 Wt%. SEM image showed no occurrence of porosity for sintered simple at 1300°C and the average grain size was observed is 7.31 um for CaP 99.25 Wt% doped 0.25 Wt% Mn and Bi 0.5 Wt%.

Keywords: Manganese, Bismuth, Calcium Phosphate.

Introduction

Calcium phosphates are the fundamental constituents of bone and teeth and play as such an essential role in our daily lives. The human bone contains 70% of calcium phosphate. Based on the logic that damaged tissue can best be repaired by something with close resemblance, biomaterials based on calcium phosphate were already shown for fracture treatment in the 1920s.

In 1970s calcium phosphate were soared in biomedical research and were approached for a broad range of orthopedic and dental applications. Based on the biomedical materials these materials are varied from thin coatings on metallic implants to aid implant fixation into the bone to sintered Calcium phosphate to be used as artificial bone graft substitutes. Calcium phosphates such as hydroxyapatite (Ca₁₀(PO₄)₆(OH)₂) HAP, fluorapatite (Ca₁₀(PO₄)₆F₂)FAp), tricalcium phosphate (Ca₃(PO₄)₂)TCP), are used for medical and dental applications. Recently clinics have reached a great success to increase the rate of the clinical survival of femoral component of total hip implants.

To diminish the danger of pin loosening for external fixators, or to allow earlier weight bearing after tibia plateau fractures. Calcium phosphate biomaterials and bioceramics are currently used as a part of various diverse applications all through the body, covering all ranges of the skeleton. Applications such as dental implants, percutaneous devices and use in periodontal treatment, treatment of bone defects, fracture treatment, total joint replacement, orthopedics, reconstruction, otolaryngology, and spinal surgery. Many years ago many implantations were failed due to the infection or

absence of knowledge about the selected materials so, based on that the use of calcium phosphate is logic due to their similarity to the mineral phase of bone and teeth.

However, based on the available literature the first use of calcium phosphate as an artificial material to repair surgically created defects in the rabbit was performed in the 1920s. Also, at that time In 1920s Triple Calcium Phosphate used aqueous slurry to stimulate bone growth, Since their initial formulation in the 1980s, calcium phosphate cement (CaP) has been increasingly, it used as bone substitutes from and 1980-1987 the study has been done on how to use CaP as coating (paint) material, 1982–1987 CaP cement ware discovered, 1985 research has been done on the Importance of microspores for bone regeneration, 1992–1999 types of research found away how to growth a Bone using CaP and resent study has been done in 2005–2013 on Re-discovery of the importance of microspores for bone formation. (Habraken, 2016).

Calcium phosphate based materials have been identified as the main candidate biomaterials for a bone implant because of its compositional and biological resemblance to host materials. HA has been the most widely studied calcium phosphate because of their close chemical similarity to minerals found in calcified tissues.

HA Mechanical properties such as strength and brittleness are very low (Fu and Chen, 2005), therefore restricts it can be used as bone implants for load-bearing application. HA reduces in body, that is why its bioactivity, but too fast degradation rate could cause negative effects, and even implants clinical failure.

Another disadvantage is designed limitations and a high degree of crystallinity which could result in the undegradebality of pure HA when it is implanted into the organ (Xiu, et al., 2005).

Problem statement

Depending on the problems that have emerged recently in some biomedical materials for people who perform total knee replacement. The weakness and defects of mechanical and physical properties in recently used materials tended to be worse. Recently used materials such as cobalt-chromium alloys it is hard, tough, corrosion-resistant material. The defect of this material can cause a reaction in the human body causing allergies especially for a patient who allergic to metals. Stainless steel has a low ability to resist corrosion in the human body in the long term. The zirconium alloy was released in 1987, has good surface coatings because they have excellent water resistance and strength but it has low systemic toxicity. Calcium phosphate is currently under study. The study on how the calcium phosphate can be used and help in biomedical application.

Objectives

The goal of this study to evaluates the addition of manganese and bismuth on the properties of calcium phosphate. To achieve this, the following objectives are selected:

- i. To study the effect of physical and mechanical properties of calcium phosphate doped with manganese and bismuth.
- ii. To observe the microstructure of the calcium phosphate when it doped with manganese and bismuth and what the average grain size also the porosity occurrence.

Scopes of work

- i. Raw materials of calcium phosphate and for the additives which are the manganese and bismuth.
- ii. Preparation of the samples in the chemical lab that were mixed together and prepared for mechanical and physical characterization.
- iii. Samples are sintered on the selected optimum temperature which is 1300°C using a furnace.
- iv. Using the lab equipment to conduct mechanical and physical characterization.
- v. The Mechanical tests that conducted are Vicker Hardness and Ultimate Compression Strength.
- vi. The Physical characterization contains Shrinkage Rate and Relative Density.
- vii. The use of SEM for the calcium phosphate doped with manganese and bismuth to determine the pores and the average grain size.

Biomaterial

During the old decades, the biomaterial ceramic-based has been defined as the biomedical application. The bioceramic material used in many biomedical applications such as dental, and orthopedics application which is the total knee replacement, and total hip implants. The use of biomaterial was due to the excellent biocompatibility and bone repair properties to the human body and it heals very well in replacing or repairing the defected bone in the human body, thus restore skeletal integrity and enhance bone healing, (C.M. Botelho et al, 2010). As a fact, the bone was important as blood where it has to be replaced and bone was most often implanted in the body as blood replaced if defective.

Calcium phosphate

Calcium phosphate (CaP) has become as biomaterials due to the excellent ability to reconstruct the defected bone in a biomedical application such as dental and orthopedic applications. It has been used in biomedical application to repair damaged bone for long years. Calcium phosphate has better tissue and excellent response by virtue of its porosity, chemical and structural similarity to that of the main composition of bone, and easily bonds with the natural bone (Ben Nissan 2003; Murugan and Ramakrishna 2005; Balazsi et al 2007).

As a biomaterial, the calcium phosphate considered the best bone graft substitutes among another biomaterial because of their performance on the rapid bone formation on their surface and it has been confirming that healing process of bone will take a year. (C.P. Klein, et al. (1985), (P.S. Egli, W. Muller, R.K. Schenk (1988). Mostly used in dense, porous or granular forms, as well as coatings of implants in the composite form (den Boer FC et al 2003, K Hing KA et al 2007).

Calcium phosphate, it was reported by Fang et al (1994) it shows high density, better microstructure, and higher strength due to the chemical composition similar to the mineral phase of bone. The human Bone consists of collagen, it possesses nanometer features, and due to its bioactive nature, CaP supports bone ingrowth without breaking or dissolving. Apart from better biocompatibility, nano HA can absorb protein strongly it has good mechanical properties (Hu et al 2007; Wilson et al 2005; Liao et al 2004).

The effect of bismuth on calcium phosphate

Bismuth (Bi_2O_3) which appeared in the 1960s. It shows excellent mechanical and physical properties to the biomaterials. Results showed that the CaP having a high content of bismuth between (0.3 – 1.0 wt %) exhibited higher densification, at low sintering temperatures (W.H.Yeo, S. Ramesh, K.L.Aw, R.Tolouei).

In term of physical properties the highest relative density of 98.8% was achieved when adding 0.3 wt% Bi was doped and sintered at 1100°C Figure 2.1. This shows that the small addition of Bi promoted the densification and porosity were reduced of CaP body at low temperature. Adding of 0.5 wt% Bi-doped CaP at 1000°C sintered temperature achieved a relative density of 98.7% while undoped CaP showed only 95.5% density at same sintering temperature. The adding of 0.5 wt% Bi-doped CaP at a lower sintered temperature of 950°C results shows poor density only 89.9%, so no additional study on this lower sintered temperature was carried out (H. Kelvin, W.D.Teng, C.Y.Tan).

Figure 1: Relative Density, CaP and Bi (H. Kelvin, W.D.Teng, C.Y.Tan).

For the mechanical properties Figure 2.2 adding of 0.5wt%, Bi-doped CaP showed higher Vickers hardness of 6 GPa compared to 5.4 GPa for undoped when sintered at a temperature of 1000°C. Higher sintered temperature 1400°C, 0.5wt % doped CaP gives lower hardness is about 4.6 GPa. For undoped showed 4.5 GPa at the same temperature (W.H.Yeo, S.Ramesh, I.Sopyan, E.Hoque, W.D.Teng).

Figure 2: Vicker Hardness, CaP and Bi (W.H.Yeo, S.Ramesh, I.Sopyan, E.Hoque, W.D.Teng).

The addition of Bi in CaP, particularly for the higher dopant concentration Figure 2.3, was found to be beneficial in increasing the youngs modulus of the sintered CaP when sintered at low temperatures. The value of 107 GPa was noted for CaP samples containing 0.5 wt% Bi when sintered at 1000°C as compared to 93 GPa for undoped CaP when sintered at a similar temperature.

Addition of 1 Wt% doped CaP showed a decrease in young modulus 71 GPa at 1350°C sintered temperature comparing with Bi undoped CaP shows increase in the young modulus about to 115 GPa at same sintering temperature.

Figure 3: Young's Modulus, CaP and Bi (W.H.Yeo, S.Ramesh, I.Sopyan, E.Hoque, W.D.Teng).

The formation of a liquid phase from additives during the sintering process is expected to improve densification and reduce the porosity. The high densification of Bi-doped CaP at low temperature could be attributed to the low melting temperature for Bi, Reported by Suchanek et al, Kalita et al, Bandyopadhyay et al, and Santos et al.

The fracture toughness was increased to 40% of CaP when 0.5 wt% Bi-doped CaP sintered at a temperature of 1000°C exhibited the highest fracture toughness which means that the Bi could increase the toughness without causing decomposition of the CaP phase. The researcher mentioned this is caused due to the liquid phase strengthens the grain boundary of the CaP structure (Kalita, S. J., Bhardwaj, A. & Bhatt, H. A).

The effect of manganese on calcium phosphate

Researchers have been studied the effect of Mn as a dopants on the stability and particle growth of CaP. The Mn dopant was doped into calcium phosphate based materials by solid state reaction and precipitation methods. Manganese was found in the bone to cause a decrease in bone resorption. It is also reported that Mn performed as calcination and sintering additives of CaP powder without producing other secondary phases like α -TCP. During the sintering process, the α -TCP phase is not preferred as it induces micro-cracks, which lead to a decrease in the mechanical properties of the sintered specimens (L.gauckler, J.F baumaro, K.kumoto, R.K boride).

It was reported that the grain growth was due to the improvement in the homogeneity of the powder with increasing the sintering temperature. Also, it occurs when sintering from 1200°C to 1400°C (N.Y mostafa, G.muralithran).

Figure Figure 4: SEM, pure CaP, Mn doped CaP.

Figure 5: SEM CaP, Mn doped CaP at 1300°C.

Figure 6: SEM pure CaP at 1300°C.

The optimum sintering temperature was at 1300°C. The sintered temperature for Mn doped CaP show increase in the densification to 99% which will play an important role during the sintering process to the biomaterial at high sintering temperature. It reduced the porosity and enhanced the growth of the grain size at this sintered temperature.

Methodology

This chapter covered the standard investigational apparatus, technique, and materials that were used throughout the research work. The Specific details relating to specific materials of experiment procedures will be described where necessary in following respective appendices. The composition of powder was selected based on background study also for the additive materials. The materials were prepared under different experimental conditions especially for calcium phosphate. Samples were prepared and characterized for mechanical and physical properties for the selected material. The tests that will be covered in this study hardness, compression, density, and shrinkage tests.

Experimental Method

The experimental method was containing mixing, compaction, sintering temperature, physical, mechanical properties, microstructure, and followed by characterization. The steps are explained in the following sections. The flow diagram of the research presented in Figure 3.1.

Figure 7: Flow Diagram of the Process

Design of experiment

The calcium phosphate bioceramics powder was prepared with different weight percentage Table 1. The samples were made by mixing the CaP with Mn and Bi. Different weight percentages were added to CaP powder. Then, mixtures were stirred to form a homogeneous paste by adding ethanol which was then packed into the molds to form samples after hardening for 24 hours; then samples were removed from the molds.

Table 1: Experiment Design.

Experiment compositions	Wt % CaP	Wt % manganese (Mn)	Wt % Bismuth (Bi)	Sintering temperature (°C)
1	100 %	0 %	0 %	1300°C
2	99.65 %	0.25 %	0.1 %	
3	99.45 %	0.25 %	0.3 %	
4	99.25 %	0.25 %	0.5 %	
5	99.05 %	0.25 %	0.7 %	

- i. For the manganese weight percentage was constant 0.25 %. This amount has the ability to enhance the mechanical and physical properties of the CaP at high sintering temperature and also as mentioned in the literature that that different amount of Mn proved to be beneficial to enhance the Cap properties.
- ii. Bismuth weight percentage ranging (0.3 – 0.7 Wt %) is useful in increasing low temperature densification of the biomaterials, also showed a high increase in the mechanical and physical properties of biomaterials. the high content of bismuth proved to be detrimental to the densification of biomaterials more than 0.7 Wt %.
- iii. The sintering temperature 1300°C is sufficient temperature to harmonize the materials together and acquire the required properties and showed excellent properties for CaP when doped with other materials at this sintered temperature.
- iv. Preparing the samples were divided into two sections, bar mold of 5 grams and a disc mold of 2 grams. Before the mixing calculation was carried out for the number of grams for each material to mix it with the ethanol which performed the homogenous paste. The specific formula used to calculate the grams of each material:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{For bar mold of 5 grams:} & \quad \frac{(\text{material})\%}{100\%} \times 5\text{g} \\ \text{For disc mold of 2 grams:} & \quad \frac{(\text{material})\%}{100\%} \times 2\text{g} \end{aligned} \quad (\text{Equation 3.1})$$

Table 2: Bar mold of 5 grams.

Experiment compositions	Calcium phosphate (CaP)	Manganese (Mn)	Bismuth (Bi)	Sintering temperature
1	5 g	0 g	0 g	1300°C
2	4.9825 g	0.0125 g	0.005 g	
3	4.9725 g	0.0125 g	0.015 g	
4	4.9625 g	0.0125 g	0.025 g	
5	4.9525 g	0.0125 g	0.035 g	

Table 3: Disc mold of 2 grams.

Experiment compositions	Calcium phosphate (CaP)	Manganese (Mn)	Bismuth (Bi)	Sintering temperature
1	2 g	0 g	0 g	1300°C
2	1.993 g	0.005 g	0.002 g	
3	1.989 g	0.005 g	0.006 g	
4	1.985 g	0.005 g	0.01 g	
5	1.981 g	0.005 g	0.014 g	

v-Bar samples made to use in compression by using a universal testing machine to determine the (young's modulus, ultimate compressive strength). For the disc samples made to determine (Vickers hardness, density, and shrinkage rate).

Figure 9: disc sample of 2 g.

Mixing

The mixing process was carried out for 1 hour. Figure 3.4 the jar had the composition that was milled with zirconia balls. Ethanol was added in the jar as a solvent for the mixing composition. The slurry was dried in an oven at 60°C for 24 hours. The prepared mixture was packed in molds 20mm in diameter and 4mm thick. For the bar mold 60mm length, 4.5mm height and 5mm thick.

Figure 10: Zirconia Ball Milling Jar.

Pressing

Compaction is a specific method to form green shapes of sufficient strength for further handling. The prepared mixture was taken and placed in a die. The mixture was pressed using a uniaxial press displayed in Figure 11. A uniaxial single action compaction technique of 400 psi was adopted. Throughout the pressing process, the die set should be kept clean to ensure the samples are not contaminated.

Figure 11: Hydraulic Press.

Sintering

Theoretically, once the ceramic powder has been compacted into pellet size, the density is around 50% of its final theoretical density. Therefore, full densification can be achieved through sintering process whereby, the green body is heated in a sintering furnace below its melting point to allow particles consolidation to occur, in the present research, the sintering approach taken was conventional pressureless sintering. It was carried out in the furnace as shown in Figure 12

Figure 12: Furnace to Perform Conventional Sintering.

Figure 13: Schematically Diagram for Sintering Profile.

Polishing

The samples were polished in the polishing machine and Grinder Polisher as displayed in Figure 13 to remove uncleaness and to make the flat face smooth. Surface grinding and polishing were successively done using a polishing machine. The samples were ground by SiC paper of 240, 400, and 800 grades respectively. These samples were then diamond polished using 6 μm , 1 μm , and 0.05 μm diamond paste to obtain a reflective and smooth surface.

Figure 14: BUEHLER Grinder and Polisher.

Physical, Mechanical and Microstructure Characterization

The prepared samples were characterized by evaluating green and sintered density, shrinkage rate, Vickers hardness and ultimate compressive strength of material have been also measured (Relative Density, Shrinkage Rate, Vickers Hardness, Ultimate Compressive strength, and Microstructure).

Result and Discussion

In the following content showed the result that found through the entire investigation. Samples are sintered at 1300°C, this sintering temperature which is the optimum temperature that has been choosing for the selected materials to join together and have the best properties. Earlier work at lower sintering temperature 1000°C this sintering temperature showed the relative density of 88% with 1.9 wt% Mn doped CaP compared to 0.6 wt% Mn doped CaP showed 92% density at 1300°C sintering temperature. During this experiment the CaP when doped Mn and Bi Showed different and variable results based on the different weight percentage of the additives materials.

Density

Figure 15: Density, CaP doped Mn and Bi.

In figure 15 showed that the addition of CaP 99.25 Wt% doped Mn 0.25 Wt% and Bi 0.5 Wt% have the higher density of 4.52 g/cm³ compared to CaP 100 Wt% undoped Mn 0 Wt% and Bi 0 Wt% showed density of 3.79 g/cm³ at 1300°C sintered temperature. This shows an increase by about 20% in the density.

For the addition of CaP 99.45 Wt% doped Mn 0.25 Wt% and 0.3 Wt% at 1300°C sintered temperature has a density of 4.18 g/cm³ compared to CaP 100 Wt% undoped Mn 0 Wt% and Bi 0 Wt% at same sintered temperature an increase in the density of 10.3%.

The CaP of 99.65 Wt% doped Mn 0.25 Wt% and Bi 0.1 Wt% have a density of 3.66 g/cm³ compared to the CaP 99.05 Wt% doped Mn 0.25 % and Bi 0.7 Wt% showed the density of 3.89 g/cm³.

As mentioned earlier by the literature the addition of Bi (0.3 – 0.7 Wt %) increased the CaP properties compared to undoped CaP and CaP doped 0.1 Wt% Bi

Which these compositions showed the lowest density due to the less addition of Bi. For the Mn addition which was constant through the experiments as it showed earlier the different amount percentage of Mn proved to have higher densification to the CaP samples. The addition of Mn and Bi to CaP body the highest result of density approved that they can promote the densification of CaP and fulfill the pores for the CaP body when adding Bi (0.3 – 0.7 Wt%) and Mn (0.25 Wt%).

Shrinkage Rate

Figure 16: Shrinkage Rate, CaP doped Mn and Bi.

Shrinkage is the relation between the green sample and sintered sample, materials shrink about 40% during the firing process. Figure 16 shows the shrinkage rate for the compositions, for the CaP 99.25 Wt% doped Mn 0.25 Wt% and Bi 0.5 Wt% shrinks about 18.20% which is the lowest shrinkage rate compared to the other compositions. The following shrinkage rate for CaP of 99.45 Wt% doped Mn 0.25 Wt% and Bi 0.3 Wt% shrinks 20.85%.

Microstructure (SEM) of calcium phosphate doped Mn and Bi

Based on the best result that was shown of the Vicker hardness the SEM image showed the average grain size and how the porosity occurrence. The addition of CaP 99.25 Wt% doped Mn 0.25 Wt% and Bi 0.5 Wt% at sintering temperature 1300°C showed no occur of the porosity at this sintered temperature as shown in Figure 17. As mentioned earlier in literature increasing the temperature (1000°C – 1400°C) showed reduce in the porosity for the material. The average grain size that was observed is 7.31 μm at 1300°C sintered temperature.

Figure 17: SEM Image, CaP 99.25 Wt% doped Mn 0.25 Wt% and Bi 0.5 Wt%.

For the addition CaP, 99.65 Wt% doped Mn 0.25 Wt% and Bi 0.1 Wt%, also the occurrence of the porosity was not shown by the SEM image at 1300°C sintered temperature Figure 18. The average grain size was reduced to 4.01 μm . For the CaP 99.05 Wt% doped Mn 0.25 Wt% and Bi 0.7 Wt% average grain size observed is 2.21 μm , for the porosity was clearly not occurred at 1300°C sintered temperature Figure 19.

The sintering temperature 1300°C reduced the porosity and enhanced the growth of the grain size at this sintered temperature. Average grain size that observed ranging from 2 μm – 7 μm when comparing with the literature that mentioned the average grain size is ranging from 3 – 6 μm at 1300°C.

Figure 18: SEM Image, Cap 99.65 Wt% doped Mn 0.25 Wt% and Bi 0.1 Wt%.

Figure 19: SEM Image, Cap 99.05 Wt% doped Mn 0.25 Wt% and Bi 0.7 Wt%.

Conclusion

- i. The density of calcium phosphate doped with manganese and bismuth at 1300°C sintered temperature showed two experiments compositions with the highest density of 4.52 g/cm^3 when CaP 99.25 Wt%

- doped 0.25 Wt% Mn and Bi 0.5 Wt% (experiment 4). Also, the CaP 99.45 Wt% doped 0.25 Wt% Mn and Bi 0.3 Wt% showed a density of 4.18 g/cm³ (experiment 3).
- ii. The shrinkage rate observes the lowest material that shrinks which is beneficial in knowing the stronger and higher quality of the materials composition. For CaP 99.25 Wt% doped 0.25 Wt% Mn and Bi 0.5 Wt% shrinks 18.20% the lowest shrinkage rate that was observed (experiment 4). For CaP 99.45 Wt% doped 0.25 Wt% Mn and Bi 0.3 Wt% shrinks about 20.85% (experiment 3).
 - iii. The highest value of vicker hardness that was observed is 378.3 HV for CaP 99.25 Wt% doped 0.25 Wt% Mn and Bi 0.5 Wt% (experiment 4). The Cp 99.65 Wt% doped 0.25 Wt% Mn and Bi 0.1 Wt% showed hardness of 373.15 HV (experiment 2).
 - iv. The ultimate compressive strength for CaP 99.45 Wt% doped 0.25 Wt% Mn and Bi 0.3 Wt% was the best of 15093.2 N (experiment 3). The addition of CaP 99.25 Wt% doped 0.25 Wt% Mn and Bi 0.5 Wt% showed lower compressive strength of 15040.1 N (experiment 4).
 - v. The material that withstands changes in length under compression when the addition of CaP 99.45 Wt% doped 0.25 Wt% Mn and Bi 0.3 Wt% young's modulus of 5.74 GPa (experiment 3). The young modulus of CaP 99.25 Wt% doped 0.25 Wt% Mn and Bi 0.5 Wt% was observed is 4.64 GPa (experiment 4).
 - vi. The SEM image for the CaP 99.25 Wt% doped 0.25 Wt% Mn and Bi 0.5 Wt% that the occurrence of porosity wasn't found and average grain size of 7.31 μ m.
 - vii. In general, the addition of CaP 99.25 Wt% doped 0.25 Wt% Mn and Bi 0.5 Wt% was identified as the optimum amount to promote densification as well as to improve the mechanical and physical properties of sintered CaP at a sintered temperature of 1300°C.

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